

Synthesis and Investigation of Zinc(II) Nitrate Complexes With Thiadiazole-1,3,4 Derivatives

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Abstract:

This article presents methods for the synthesis of new complex compounds of zinc(II) with 2-aminothiadiazole-1,3,4 (AT) structure $[Zn(AT)_3(NO_3)_2]$ and 2-amino-5-methylthiadiazole-1,3,4 (AMT) structure $[Zn(AMT)_3(NO_3)_2]$. The structure of the obtained complexes was established by the methods of elemental and X-ray diffraction analyses. In complexes around the Zn(II) ion, three nitrogen atoms of thiadiazole cycles and two oxygen atoms of two nitrate anions are coordinated in the equatorial plane in axial positions.

Keywords: 2-Aminothiadiazole-1, 3,4, 2-amino-5-methylthiadiazole-1,3,4, X-ray diffraction analysis, polyhedron, trigonal bipyramide.

Introduction. Of particular interest are biologically active heterocyclic compounds that are used in medicine, veterinary medicine, agriculture and other areas of the national economy [1-9]. Among polydentate organic ligands in the chemistry of complex compounds, 2-aminothiadiazole-1,3,4 and its derivatives are of important interest [10-17]. This is due to the presence of several donor atoms in their composition and their widespread use in medical practice, agriculture and industry [18-24].

Previously, we reported on the synthesis and crystal structure of a complex of zinc(II) halides with 2-aminothiadiazole-1,3,4 (AT) of the composition $[\text{Zn}(\text{AT})_2\text{X}_2]$ (where X is Cl, Br, I) [25-27]. In the crystal of the complex around the central halide ion, the resulting complex has a distorted tetrahedral coordination sphere consisting of two coordinated nitrogen atoms of the thiadiazole rings of two L and two halide atoms. In the case when the ligand is 2-amino-5-ethylthiadiazole-1,3,4 (AET), the complex is a distorted tetrahedron, at the vertices of which there are three nitrogen atoms of three ligand molecules and an oxygen atom of a water molecule, nitrate anions are located in the outer sphere of the complex $[\text{Zn}(\text{AET})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})](\text{NO}_3)_2$ [28].

In contrast to these works, this work is devoted to the results of the synthesis and study of the crystalline and molecular structure of the zinc(II) nitrate complex with 2-amino-5-R-thiadiazole-1,3,4 synthesized according to the equation (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. ligands: R= – H (I, AT), – CH₃ (II, AMT); complexes: R= – H (III), – CH₃ (IV);

Zinc(II) nitrate forms a five-coordination complex compound with 2-amino-5-R-thiadiazole-1,3,4 (R= –H and –CH₃). The increase in the coordination number in this case is obviously explained by the large repulsion of voluminous nitrate ions located around the central ion from each other. As a result, it becomes possible to coordinate to the central atom of the third molecule of the heterocycle. The resulting complexes of $[\text{Zn}(\text{AT})_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ – III and $[\text{Zn}(\text{AMT})_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ – IV zinc nitrate with aminothiadiazoles of the coordination polyhedron represent a trigonal bipyramide, in the equatorial plane of which there are three nitrogen atoms of three heterocycle molecules; the axial positions of the polyhedron are occupied by oxygen atoms of two nitrates-anions, the coordination sphere in the complexes $[\text{Zn}(\text{AT})_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ – III and $[\text{Zn}(\text{AMT})_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ – IV trigonal bipyramide.

The experimental part.

Synthesis of the $[\text{Zn}(\text{AMT})_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ complex. For the synthesis of this complex, a hot solution of 1,036 g (0.009 mol) of AMT ligand in 50 ml of ethanol was added with gradual stirring, a hot solution of 0.57 g (0.003 mol) of zinc (II) nitrate in 50 ml of ethanol, then heated with a reverse refrigerator for an hour, filtered and left for crystallization. After a day, the fallen beige crystals were filtered and dried in air.

Elemental analysis of compounds on C, H, N was performed on the EA 1108 device of the Carlo Erba company, Zn was determined on the 3030V device of the Perkin Elmer company.

III: pale yellowish crystals, T_m. -195°C, yield 1.36 g (85.0% based on $[\text{ZnL}_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$).

Found, %: C 20.65; H 2.94; N 28.42; Zn 12.12.

As for C₉H₁₅N₁₁S₃O₆Zn

calculated, % C 20.21; H 2.83; N 28.81; Zn 12.22.

The complex is synthesized in a similar way $[\text{ZnL}^1_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ (IV) [29-31].

IV: pale yellowish crystals, Tm. – 183-85 °C, output 1,24 g (84,0 % based on $[\text{ZnL}^1_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$).

found, %: C 14.48; H 2.13; N 31.21; Zn 13.09.

As for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{N}_{11}\text{S}_3\text{O}_6\text{Zn}$

calculated, % C 14.62; H 1.84; N 31.27; Zn 13.27.

Research methodology. The crystallographic parameters for crystal structure III were determined and refined from 15 reflections on an automatic four-circle diffractometer Syntex-P21 at room temperature. It is established that the isolated crystals are triclinic with parameters: $a=7.563(2)$, $b=8.033(3)$, $c=14.741(4)$ Å, $\alpha=100.17(2)^\circ$, $\beta=91.58(2)^\circ$, $\gamma=101.96(2)^\circ$, $V=860.4(0.9)\text{Å}^3$, $Z=2$, $d = 1.902 \text{ g/cm}^3$, spatial group $P-1$, $R=0.057$, $R_w = 0.057$ [12, 27, 29-30].

For the crystal structure IV, X-ray diffraction analysis was performed on an X taLA B Synergy diffractometer (Rigaku, Japan) installed in the Center for Collective Use of the Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The experiments were carried out using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation (mirror monochromator, 3D scanning). Triclinic crystals: $a=8.4152(3)$, $b=8.43370(16)$, $c=12.9394(5)$ Å, $\alpha=84.562(2)^\circ$, $\beta=85.949^\circ$, $\gamma=67.892(3)^\circ$, $V=846.37(5)\text{Å}^3$, $Z=2$, $d = 1.624 \text{ g/cm}^3$, spatial group $P-1$, $R=0.027$, $R_w = 0.072$ (fig. 1.).

The results obtained and their discussion

The compared distances, angles and deviations in the polyhedra of the complexes are as follows: the zinc atom leaves the equatorial plane of the bipyramide by 0.088 Å(III), 0.071 Å (IV) towards the O(1B) atom (Fig. 1). The zinc-oxygen distances in the axial positions of the bipyramide are not the same: Zn(1)-O(1A) 2.460(8) (III), 2.331(5) Å (IV) and Zn(1)-O(1B) 2.191(6) (III), 2.169(4) (IV) Å [29-30];

A coordination node is formed in the equatorial plane of the bipyramid Zn(1), N(1A), N(1B), N(1C). The angles between the “middle” plane of this coordination node and the “middle” planes of the five-membered heterocycles N(1A), N(2A), C(1A), C(2A), S(1A); N(1B), N(2B), C(1B), C(2B), S(1B) и N(1C), N(2C), C(1C), C(2C), S(1C) contain 19.4°, 11.7° and 7.2° (III); 30.7°, 28.0° and 31.2° (IV) Accordingly, this seems to be explained by a change in the ligand molecule, where the complex (III) was replaced by a methyl group (IV) instead of the hydrogen atom.

Fig.1. The molecular structure of the complex $[\text{Zn}(\text{AMT})_3(\text{NO}_3)_2]$.

Bond lengths and valence angles in the three independent ligands of the AMT complex are in good agreement with each other. The C-S distances (1.730(6)-1.741(8) Å) lie within the usual lengths of carbon-sulfur bonds, the N-N distances are in the range 1.374(7)-1.387(7) Å and correspond to standard values for single bonds in a five-membered heterocycle [31-32].

Analysis of intra- and intermolecular contacts in the studied structure showed that there are two types of hydrogen bonds in the complex molecule, intramolecular (IntraMHB) and intermolecular (InterMHB) [11]. Comparing IntraMHB between molecules, an interesting fact is observed, in molecule III, each NH₂ group of the thiadiazole ring participates in the formation of IntraMHB N-N···N with uncoordinated nitrogen atoms of the neighboring polyhedron molecule, and in molecule IV, in two cases, such IntraMHB as N-N···N are formed, and in the other case IntraMHB – N-N···O with an oxygen atom of the nitrate anion. These values also come true when the "middle" plane of the coordination polyhedron of the central atom Zn, N(1A), N(1B), N1(C) and the "middle" planes of the five-membered heterocycles are 7.2-19.4° in molecule III and 28.0-31.2° in molecule IV, respectively [30-33]. The deviation of the exocyclic nitrogen atoms of the amino groups from the "average" planes of the aminothiadiazole heterocycles is in the range of 0.003–0.057 Å and -0.014–0.023 Å in molecules III and IV, respectively.

In both cases, when packing a molecule in crystals, InterMHB are formed – nitrogen atoms of the NH₂ group form bonds with oxygen atoms of the nitrate ion and an uncoordinated nitrogen atom of neighboring molecules.

Conclusion. Thus, new zinc complexes were synthesized: 2-aminothiadiazole-1,3,4 (AT), with the structure [Zn(AT)₃(NO₃)₂] and 2-amino-5-methylthiadiazole-1,3,4 (AMT), with the structure [Zn(AMT)₃(NO₃)₂]. As a result of XRD studies, it was found that during the complexation of ligands, they are coordinated through an endocyclic nitrogen atom, which is in the α position relative to the amino group.

The polyhedron of the central atoms is a trigonal bipyramide, in the coordination sphere of which there are three nitrogen atoms in the equatorial plane and two oxygen atoms of nitrate anions in an axial position.

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